

Mini-Review

The Role of Surgery in Primary Central Nervous System Lymphomas (PCNSL)

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Abstract

Primary central nervous system lymphoma (PCNSL) is a rare extranodal non-Hodgkin lymphoma confined to the CNS, historically treated with chemotherapy and radiotherapy. Surgery has primarily been limited to biopsy due to the tumor's diffuse nature and sensitivity to chemotherapy. However, recent advancements in neurosurgical techniques have prompted reevaluation of the role of surgery. Select patients with solitary, well-circumscribed lesions or life-threatening mass effects may benefit from surgical intervention. Advances such as minimally invasive techniques, neuronavigation, and fluorescence-guided surgery have enhanced the safety and precision of resections. Integrating surgery with chemotherapy or radiotherapy may improve local control and patient outcomes. Molecular profiling and

personalized treatment strategies are being investigated to further refine the role of surgery in PCNSL management. While surgery is not yet a primary treatment, its evolving role offers potential benefits in carefully selected cases.

Introduction

Primary Central Nervous System Lymphoma (PCNSL) is a rare form of extranodal non-Hodgkin lymphoma confined to the CNS, accounting for less than 5% of all primary brain tumors (Schaff & Grommes, 2021). PCNSL primarily affects immunocompromised individuals, such as those with HIV/AIDS, but it also occurs in immunocompetent patients. The standard treatment for PCNSL has traditionally been non-surgical, focusing on high-dose methotrexate (HD-MTX)-based chemotherapy with or without whole-brain radiotherapy (WBRT), particularly because of the tumor's high sensitivity to these treatments (Löw et al., 2018). Historically, surgery has been limited to diagnostic biopsy, with resection avoided due to concerns over the diffuse, infiltrative nature of the tumor and its responsiveness to non-surgical interventions (Hoang-Xuan et al., 2022).

However, recent advances in neurosurgical techniques and growing interest in personalized treatment strategies have led to renewed discussion regarding the role of surgery in the management of PCNSL. This Mini- review provides a look at the surgical management of PCNSL, focusing on indications, patient selection, advances in neurosurgical techniques, and integration with multimodal therapies.

Historical Role of Surgery in

PCNSL

Historically, surgical resection has not played a prominent role in the management of PCNSL, largely due to the tumor's diffuse and infiltrative nature. Early studies in the 1990s established that aggressive surgical approaches did not improve survival and were associated with significant morbidity (Lw et al., 2018). The widespread use of corticosteroids, which can cause temporary regression of the tumor, further complicated the surgical approach, as this often led to the "disappearance" of the tumor on imaging, making resection challenging (Schaff & Grommes, 2021). As a result, surgery was primarily reserved for stereotactic biopsy to obtain a histopathological diagnosis.

Indications for Surgery in PCNSL:

Modern Perspectives

In recent years, the role of surgery in PCNSL has evolved, particularly in light of advancements in neurosurgical technologies and better patient selection criteria. While chemotherapy remains the cornerstone of treatment, there is growing evidence supporting the use of surgery in specific circumstances, such as:

1. **Solitary, Well-Circumscribed Lesions:** Surgery may be beneficial for patients with solitary, well-defined lesions that are causing significant mass effect or increased intracranial pressure. In these cases, resection can provide immediate relief from symptoms such as headache, nausea, or neurological

deficits caused by elevated intracranial pressure (Weller et al., 2018). A study by Gempt et al. (2012) suggested that patients who underwent gross total resection of localized lesions showed improved outcomes compared to those who underwent biopsy alone, although the overall survival benefit remains controversial.

2. **Life-Threatening Mass Effect:** For patients with large lesions causing significant mass effect, surgical decompression may be necessary to alleviate symptoms such as obstructive hydrocephalus. In such cases, the primary goal of surgery is to relieve pressure on surrounding brain structures rather than achieving complete tumor resection (Hoang-Xuan et al., 2022). This is particularly important in cases where immediate chemotherapy may not produce rapid enough results to prevent herniation or other life-threatening complications.
3. **Failure of Non-Invasive Diagnostics:** In rare cases, when non-invasive imaging fails to provide a definitive diagnosis, open craniotomy may be necessary to obtain a larger tissue sample for molecular and histopathological analysis (Renaud et al., 2021). This is particularly relevant in patients who present with atypical imaging findings that could mimic other pathologies, such as gliomas or metastatic disease.

Advances in Neurosurgical

Techniques

The development of minimally invasive surgical techniques has significantly reduced the morbidity

associated with obtaining a tissue diagnosis for PCNSL. Stereotactic biopsy remains the gold standard for diagnosis, allowing for precise targeting of lesions in deep or eloquent brain areas with minimal risk (Weller et al., 2018). The integration of neuronavigation systems and intraoperative imaging, such as MRI and PET, has improved the accuracy of these procedures and reduced complications.

In addition to stereotactic biopsy, newer techniques, such as endoscopic surgery and robot-assisted interventions, are being explored for their potential benefits in PCNSL management (Cui et al., 2023). For example, endoscopic approaches have been used to access lesions located in the ventricles or near the brainstem, where traditional open surgery would carry significant risks. These techniques offer the advantage of reduced recovery times and lower complication rates, particularly in elderly or frail patients.

One of the most promising developments in neurosurgery for PCNSL is the application of fluorescence-guided surgery (FGS). This technique involves the use of fluorescent dyes that selectively accumulate in tumor tissue, allowing for more precise resection while minimizing damage to surrounding healthy brain structures (Wendler et al., 2022). Although FGS is primarily used in glioma surgery, its application in PCNSL is being investigated as a way to improve diagnostic accuracy and reduce the risk of residual tumor tissue following resection.

Integration of Surgery with Multimodal Therapy

While surgery alone is rarely curative in PCNSL, its role as part of a multimodal treatment strategy is gaining attention. The integration of surgery with chemotherapy and radiotherapy aims to improve local control of the tumor, reduce relapse rates, and enhance the efficacy of systemic therapies.

- Surgery and Chemotherapy:** High-dose methotrexate (HD-MTX)-based chemotherapy remains the cornerstone of PCNSL treatment. However, there is emerging evidence suggesting that cytoreductive surgery—the removal of as much tumor mass as possible—may enhance the efficacy of chemotherapy by reducing the tumor burden and improving drug delivery to the remaining tumor cells (Schaff & Grommes, 2021). This approach is particularly relevant in patients with bulky disease, where chemotherapy alone may not be sufficient to achieve complete remission.
- Surgery and Radiotherapy:** The combination of surgery and radiotherapy is also being explored, particularly in cases where surgery can reduce the tumor mass, allowing for more targeted radiation treatment (Löv et al., 2018). While WBRT has traditionally been used in PCNSL, its associated neurotoxicity, particularly in elderly patients, has led to the development of more localized radiation techniques, such as stereotactic radiosurgery (SRS). When combined with surgical resection, SRS can provide durable local control while minimizing the side effects of radiation.
- Molecular and Genetic Profiling:** One of the most exciting areas of research in PCNSL

management is the use of molecular and genetic profiling to guide treatment decisions. Emerging evidence suggests that patients with specific genetic mutations, such as MYD88 or CD79B mutations, may benefit from tailored treatment approaches, including surgery combined with targeted therapies (Baraniskin & Schroers, 2021). By integrating molecular profiling into the decision-making process, clinicians can identify patients who are most likely to benefit from surgery and other aggressive treatments.

Outcomes and Prognostic Factors

The outcomes of surgical intervention in PCNSL vary widely depending on several factors, including the extent of resection, tumor location, and patient characteristics.

While gross total resection (GTR) may improve progression-free survival in select patients, it is not always associated with improved overall survival, particularly in patients with diffuse or multifocal disease (Gempt et al., 2012). Factors such as patient age, performance status, and response to chemotherapy are often more predictive of long-term outcomes than the extent of surgery (Renaud et al., 2021).

Recent studies have highlighted the importance of molecular markers in predicting outcomes following surgical intervention. For example, patients with MYD88 mutations tend to have a poorer prognosis, even when treated with aggressive multimodal therapy (Baraniskin & Schroers, 2021). As a result, the use of molecular profiling to guide surgical decision-making is likely to play an increasingly important role in the future of PCNSL management.

Conclusion

The role of surgery in the management of PCNSL is evolving, driven by advances in neurosurgical techniques, better patient selection, and a growing understanding of the molecular and genetic factors that influence tumor behavior. While surgery is unlikely to replace chemotherapy as the primary treatment modality, it can provide significant benefits in select cases, particularly when integrated into a multimodal treatment approach. Future research should focus on refining the indications for surgery, improving patient selection criteria, and exploring the potential of combining surgery with emerging therapies, such as immunotherapy and targeted molecular treatments.

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